

Critical Discourse Analysis Of Newspapers' Articles: CPEC In The Lens Of Lexicalization

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ABSTRACT

CPEC, the phenomenon economically significant in Pakistan has been studied theoretically through critical discourse analysis of ideology in multiple studies however; the studies on how such ideologies are lexically accounted are observed scanty in literature. Given the fact that ideologies are very crucial in dealing with the subject like CPEC in print media in Pakistan, this study investigates the ways the news gets covered in the Pakistani leading English /Urdu newspapers: The News and Daily Dawn/ Daily Jang and The Express expressing the ideological pursuits of economical phenomenon. The main objective of the study is to investigate the lexical items used in English newspapers in Pakistan dealing the economical news like CPEC. This paper adopts the theoretical model by Fairclough that is equivalent to Halliday's theoretical model on 'lexicalisation'. The findings indicate that same news subject has been depicted with different tone affecting the intensity of the news. The study is distinctive in its nature for its originality as it is interdisciplinary study and its findings are in line with the existing literature on media conflict.

Keywords: Critical Discourse Analysis; CPEC, Halliday Model; Lexicalization

1. Introduction

In recent times of March 2020, the arrest of Mir Shakil-ur-Rehman, the editor Jang/Geo was marked unlawful and condemned by the journalists in Pakistan. “It is essentially a battle of media freedom in Pakistan that must be waged and won at all costs” (the news.com, Mar.2020). The statement contradicts with the statement of Prime Minister, Imran Khan who stated confidently on his visit to America, “Pakistan's media, in my opinion, is freer than Britain's.” (July.23, 2019). Imran Khan seems claiming for media freedom in Pakistan but the other school of thought seems complaining that media is under the influence of the power.

The controversy observed in above statements raise a question on the role of media in Pakistan. What is media meant for? It is to impart the news and information or it is to propagate as per the state governs. Principally speaking, media should be free from the mechanism of propaganda. It should be unbiased aiming at providing the news to the masses. Realistically, it is media that educates people. Media needs to serve as an institution. Li (2009) presents media as a “social and discursive institution which regulates and organizes social life as well as the production of social knowledge, values, and beliefs through linguistic means” (cited in Parvez, 2015, p.31). Thus, Media is a source of information with a role to impart knowledge in a way as the news exists. However; media spreads ‘fake news’ as well. Fake news may be the exaggeration of any existed news or may be presented with a completely new dimension.

Media in Pakistan is under harsh criticism at both the national and international level. “The approach of media in Pakistan is business oriented where sensationalism is used as a tool to attract the financier and buyers” (Hussain, 2012). This statement presents media playing a negative role in the projection of news. The lexical items play a significant role in news projection. The choice of words that are made by the writer affects the meaning conveyed in the news. A very simple question of what makes the writer choose specific words for spreading any news needs attention of the researchers in the current era of media supremacy.

1.1.Problem Statement

News is projected differently by different newspapers presenting different ideologies on the same subject prevailing in the society. The different projections of the news make the news unauthentic and unreliable. More recent distension of the apparent problems in representation of news has become even more identified as it has been noted in various articles and public discussion in Pakistan. For example, the study conducted by Lodhi et al.(2019) reveals that “In the past, print media in Pakistan had the status of being objective and mature source of information but recently popular and crispy style is being adopted to enhance ratings in the race of profit”. His study explored that the media uses different linguistic features and linguistic deviations on deliberate purpose to construct or mould certain ideology in the society at national and international forum. The different representations of the same news pave the way for the current research to study on ideology construction focusing lexicalization.

1.3 Research Questions

The major questions addressed through this research are as following:

RQ1: What ideology is constructed about CPEC, an economical phenomenon, in English/Urdu newspapers in Pakistan through Lexicalization?

RQ2: What differences are observed in discursive features through lexical items used in English/Urdu articles dealing with the economical subject CPEC?

1.4 Significance of the Study

The study being interdisciplinary is significant in the domain of discourse studies. Lexicalization is very helpful in understanding the ideological meanings of the text used in newspapers. It's a crucial framework for interpreting words into meaning. This study may be useful for language researchers who are analysing and interpreting written texts from various linguistics tools. The study opens up new avenues for researchers to explore discourse and style in different forms of linguistics using lexicalization.

2. CDA: A Conceptual Framework

In the views of Fairclough & Wodak (1997) the critical discourse analysis serves in text analysis along with the task of revealing truth that is unheard. Its competence encompasses not only a wide range of methods for text analysis, but also a domain that reveals many underlying truths, values, and cross-cultural challenges. Furthermore, it emphasizes historical themes as well as norms. However, the majority of people around the world have misread this statement. The majority of people link it with text and spoken discourse feelings, however it is actually about exploring the complexity, informal rejection, and multiple standards of text and spoken discourse. It necessitates a balance of theory and phenomena. Its expertise is not only an area that provides a numerous tools for text observation but it is a domain that unfolds many unspoken truths, values and cross-cultural issues. Furthermore, it also highlights the historical aspects and conventions as well. However, this expression has been misinterpreted by most of the people across the world. Most of the people associate it with feelings of the text and spoken discourse but in fact it is about to explore the complexity, informal rejection and dual standards of text and spoken discourse. It requires a balanced between theory and phenomena (Wodak, 1999; 1996).

Discourse, according to Fairclough (1995), is "the language employed to depict a certain social practise from a particular point of view." (quoted on p. 33 in Bartley, 2017). In this case, discourse is the building of social structures that are significantly impacted by social ideals.

The Fairclough Model is crucial in many ways, including the fact that it allows the analyst to focus on the text's signifiers, precise language selections, juxtapositioning, sequencing, and layout. Textual analysis, according to Fairclough (1992), is carried out using multifunctional theories of language, such as systematic-functional linguistics. This includes grammar and other components of language that make the connection between the text and its social settings. The analysis does

not focus solely on what is contained in a text, but also on what is not included in a text that may have meaning. Fairclough's method is effective because it concentrates on the text on numerous levels. There are no gaps in the multi-layered analysis.

2.1 CDA Scope in Pakistan

In recent years, critical discourse analysis has gained a lot of attraction in Pakistan. Several attempts have been made in the field of CDA (Alam et al., 2017; Gopang & Bughio, 2015; Mahmood et al., 2014; and Bilal et al., 2012 etc). These researches show that CDA is becoming a research repository in Pakistan. Attempts to analyse these characteristics can reveal the governing body's power or influence. Critical Discourse Analysis of newspaper articles may reveal the various depictions of the same news storey. The study Textual and Rhetoric Analysis of English and Urdu News Headlines by Lodhi and colleagues (2019) is an attempt to scrutinise print media news headlines by using textual and rhetorical analysis. The findings show that discursive features used in various media vary. Similarly, Hayat and Juliana released a study in 2016 called Comparative Analysis of Pakistani English Newspaper Editorials on the Taliban's Attack on Malala Yousuf Zai. After the Taliban attempted to assassinate Malala Yousaf Zai, the study looked at how she was depicted in four Pakistani English newspapers. In some blogs, Malala Yousuf Zai was portrayed as a victim as well as an American spy. The various portrayals of Malalayousuf Zai are indicative of different editors' ideologies, which can be revealed through critical discourse study. The value of the same news can also be shown by critical discourse analysis. In 2017, Alam et al. published a report to examine how the Pakistani print media covered the dispute. The problem in Baluchistan was a nationalist conflict centred on a dispute between the government and the judiciary. According to the findings, the Baluchistan conflict has received no attention in Pakistani newspapers.

2.2 Lexicalization:

The lexical objects used by the writer to express meaning to the reader are referred to as lexicalization. Fairclough (1992) coined the phrase "wording" to describe lexicalization, and he saw it as a source of a writer's opinion reflection. The writer's point of view is reflected in the terms he or she chooses. When it comes to conveying meaning, words are crucial. The text's foundations are the lexical objects. Depending on their preference and meaning, various editors use different lexical objects. News discourse may use implicit strategies to mask attitudes and judgments in word choices. Van Dijk (1988) investigates the role of linguistic devices in shaping public perception in Pakistani media discourse. Lexical decisions could have semantic ramifications. Some theorists believe the lexical terms that express caring judgments should not be included in news reporting (Bigot, Terrier, Jamet, Botherel, and Rouet, 2010). Apart from that, the editors use terms according to their preference, purpose, context, social needs, and newspaper policy. The choosing of terms with diverse connotations are the most common lexical issues. It is a popular belief that when referring to the same individual or social issue, a language user typically has a

number of terms to choose from, which are classified according to personal, social, and cultural settings. It is thought that this decision is usually made on the basis of ideology.

3. Method

3.1. Research Approach

The study follows qualitative approach exploratory in nature. According to Maxwell, “The qualitative inquiry is especially suitable for five specific goals, such as ‘understanding the purpose,’ ‘understanding the particular context,’ ‘identifying unanticipated phenomena,’ ‘understanding the mechanism,’ and ‘developing causal explanations’” (2005). In the current study, the focus gets matched with the features of qualitative study.

3.2 Framework of the Study

This study's major theoretical framework was Critical Discourse Analysis, which was used to analyse news discourse critically and discover how it affects society. CDA is defined by Van Dijk (2001b) as a sort of discourse analysis "that principally investigates the way social power abuse, domination, and inequality are enacted, reproduced, and resisted in a social setting through text and talk" (p.352). The current study's goal is similar to critical discourse analysis' goal.

3.3. Data Collection

The articles from two leading English newspapers and two Urdu newspapers have been selected through purposive sampling. According to Patton (1990), in qualitative analysis, sampling is almost always purposeful neither probability nor convenience. The articles for the current study were selected on the basis of node of the article that served the purpose of the study. The node is the central idea of an article. All articles with the node of CPEC concept as how people view it in the frame of Pakistan economy published in the period of 2016-2017 have been chosen for the sample of the current study.

3.4. Research Procedure

The research was carried out qualitatively following these steps:

- The articles from Daily Dawn & THE NEWS/ Daily Jang & the Express were selected considering the node CPEC as an economical project from the period of 2016-17.
- The main lexical items associated with the node were selected and interpreted in comparison.
- Finally, the discussion was made in relation to the existing literature.

4. Findings & Discussion

The node of the current study is based on the lexical items that originated from the selected papers. The study's node revolves around the influence of CPEC, which can be framed in newspapers as either PRO-CPEC or ANTI-CPEC. The research looks at the CPEC, which is a national economic phenomenon. It was assumed that the pro-CPEC agenda will dominate the media, and this has proven to be true in the current study. However; the discursive practices in presenting this ideology have been observed through different lexical items that are under the discussion below:

Daily Dawn	The News
Game changer	game changer in economy and strength
transform the entire region	will change the face of Karachi but of entire province
mega project	mega project
turn a new leaf	bring good fortune to KPK
bring peace, prosperity, and opportunities	usher in a new era of development and prosperity in KPK
way of hope and future	opened new vistas of foreign investment
bring new know-how to Pakistan	gift of China
deepens relationship of trust	game changer in real sense
raises friendship to newer heights	given new start to Pak- china friendship
jewel in the CPEC crown	immense benefits

hailed as master piece of Pak-China relationship	of progress
project of development and prosperity	on the way to progress
eliminate poverty and unemployment	play a role in alleviating poverty, and elimination of terrorism and fanaticism
bring political stability	will change the course of history
generate thousands of jobs	integrate development and commerce of various region

Table 1: Lexical Items used in Daily Dawn & The News newspapers Representing CPEC

The above table indicates the different lexical items used for CPEC in different newspapers. Taking some examples from above table, the tone of the writer and the intensity in the words can be observed used for spreading the ideology.

- **Eliminate Poverty & Unemployment vs. Alleviate Poverty and Eliminate Terrorism & Fanaticism**

In both newspapers, the writers discuss CPEC as a means of alleviating poverty; however, the terms 'eliminate' and 'alleviate' are used differently in Daily Dawn and THE NEWS, respectively. The verb 'eliminate' means 'to put an end to,' whereas the verb 'alleviate' means 'to partially remove,' according to Merriam dictionary. The Daily Dawn makes the bold argument that CPEC would absolutely eradicate poverty. The tone here seems to be interpretive. The author argues that CPEC is so advantageous that it would eliminate poverty and unemployment. When presenting CPEC, the writer has developed a sense of urgency. Over here, CPEC has been assigned the highest elevations. The sound of THE NEWS, on the other hand, seems to be very neutral. Though the writer maintains the viewpoint that CPEC is useful, he does not deal with it in an ideal manner. The verb option 'alleviate' conveys the true benefits of CPEC, which include the ability to partly alleviate poverty. Terrorism and fanaticism have also been defined using the word "eliminate. Since all political parties agree on the advantages of the CPEC, violent activity can be reduced. In presenting CPEC, the tone is less emotional and more neutral.

- **'mega project' vs. 'mega project in real sense'**

In both media, CPEC has been portrayed as a megaproject. The general consensus is that CPEC is a massive project with outstanding results. This viewpoint is shared by both the speakers and the authors. However, Shahbaz Sharif, Punjab's Chief Minister, said in THE NEWS that "CPEC is a mega project in the true sense." The position that CPEC is a mega project remains unchanged, but

the speaker seems to be less certain of its benefits. The speaker seems to require the addition of the word "in real sense" in order to persuade others of his point of view. The term "mega" was also used in THE NEWS to describe the CPEC project, which has a small reach, as a "mega project in economy and power." To make it more realistic than ideal, the boundary line has been drawn over here. CPEC isn't a magic wand that magically transforms all negative situations into positive ones. This is an example of lexical absence or repression. Lexical items are more required to explain CPEC as mega project in Daily Dawn as how it is mega? To what extent it is mega project? These absences of information make the news less authentic

- **Way of hope and future vs. path of progress**

In both the Daily Dawn and THE NEWS newspapers, CPEC has been depicted as a means of bringing good fortune to Pakistan. "The CPEC is the way of hope and future for our region," the Prime Minister (Nawaz Sharif) said in a Daily Dawn post (Aug. 30, 2016), while Chief Minister, Shahbaz Sharif says in THE NEWS that "CPEC is the path of progress" (April.3, 2017). The distinction between abstraction and concreteness is reflected in the close examination of the terms 'way' and 'path'. The word 'way' refers to a general realization while the word 'path' refers to a concrete realization. PRO-CPEC ideology can be found in both publications, but Daily Dawn presents it through abstraction describing it as a way of optimism and the future. The NEWS, on the other hand, portrays CPEC as a road of change, and the term 'path' is a strong indication of a genuine and meaningful assertion.

- **Raises friendship to newer heights vs. give new dimension/new start to Pak-China friendship**

In Daily Dawn and The News, the words "newer heights" and "new dimension" were used to describe the future of Pak-China friendship. According to the dictionary definition, the term "newer heights" refers to an improvement that has never been seen before, while the term "dimension" refers to a measurement. In describing the future of Pakistan-China ties, there is a conceptual distinction. Daily Dawn reflects a pro-CPEC ideology, claiming that CPEC would bring Pakistan and China closer together than they have ever been before. However, The News appears to be correct in stating that a friendship between Pakistan and China already exists, but that this friendship may take on a new form in the form of a business partnership.

- **Bring new know-how to Pakistan vs. opened new vistas of foreign investment**

In the realm of simple and ambiguous phenomena, the disparity in lexis selection in the preceding examples can be discussed. The benefits of CPEC are unclear in the lexis used in Daily Dawn, which claims that it will bring new know-how to Pakistan, as mentioned by PM (Nawaz Sharif) in Daily Dawn (Aug.30, 2016). The term "know how" refers to practical knowledge and expertise, as opposed to theoretical knowledge and expertise that is contrasted with the word 'vistas' that

means views. The word ‘vistas’ has been used in The NEWS newspaper as Chief Minister (Shahbaz Sharif) said ‘CPEC has opened new vistas of foreign investment in Pakistan which would give unusual benefits to the country’ (April.3, 2017). The distinction between general and specific or non-directional and directional hypotheses can be seen here. The Daily Dawn has set an example of a non-directional hypothesis in which modern technology can either benefit or harm Pakistan. The News, on the other hand, has clearly stated the advantages of CPEC, stating that foreign investment will be allowed. This is an example of directional hypothesis.

“Some terms are politically disputed, and they indicate ideological struggle,” as theorized by Fairclough in 1989 (cited in Riyano et al.2018). This is often apparent in a document, such as the word socialism in a letter claiming that believing that a phrase like socialism has one real and literal interpretation is a semantic mistake.

4.2 Lexical Items Used for CPEC Project in Daily Jang/The Express Newspapers

The lexical items used for presenting CPEC in Urdu newspapers are discussed in the following table:

Daily Jang	The Express
khushali ki zamanat (Guarantee of Prosperity)	mulki mayishat mei reerh ki haddi ki hasiyet (a backbone in the economy of country)
bra gamechanger (big game changer)	lazawal dosti (Everlasting Friendship)
sab se bra tarraqyati mansooba (the biggest development project)	CPEC pe fakhr (Pride on CPEC)
teiz raftar iqtasadi tarraqi ki shahrah (on the way to speedy Economic development)	Pak-Cheen dosti ki bemisal alamat (exemplary sign of Pak-China friendship)
roshn mustaqbil ki naved (good news of bright future)	tarraqi ki nai lehr (new wave of development)
bra toufa (big gift)	poore khitte k liye game changer mansooba (game changer project for the entire region)
Qismat badl jaegi (fate will be changed)	doorras or taweel mudatti fawaid (far-reaching and long-lasting benefits)

Pak-Cheen dosti intihai mazboot hai (Pak-China friendship is very strong)	barish ka pehla qatra (Ist rain drop)
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Table 2: lexical Items used in Daily Jang and The Express newspapers Representing CPEC

The table above shows the wide range of lexis included in Daily Jang and Daily Express. All of these lexical items are moving around the PRO-CPEC node. If we look closely at the words used, we may see several changes that alter the writer's tone. For instance;

Example 1: Pak-Cheen dosti intihai mazboot vs. Pak-cheen dosti ki bemisaal alamat (Pak-China Friendship is very strong vs. Pak-China friendship unmatched)

These two papers report on the Pakistan-China relationship in distinct ways. These aren't just words; they convey the authors' viewpoints to the reader. In the Daily Jang and Daily Express, the linguistic options utilised to depict Pak-China friendship were 'strong' and 'unmatched.' Such terms, particularly 'unmatched,' do not ring true. A more modest phrase, such as 'good,' could be utilised. The expression 'unmatched' is an example of hyperbole since it is overblown. The CPEC project has been touted as developing a strong and unrivalled partnership between China and Pakistan, but these statements are not the result of any measured action, therefore we can say that the Daily Express is making a large claim.

Example 2: sab se bra tarraqyati mansooba vs. CPEC ki mulki mayishat mei reerh ki haddi ki hasiyet (CPEC, the biggest development project vs. CPEC as backbone in the Economy of Country)

The lexical items 'sab se bra tarraqyati mansooba (the biggest development project) in daily Jang and 'mulki mayishat mei reerh ki haddi ki hasiyet' (CPEC as backbone in Economy of country) in Daily Express are observed being used to describe the CPEC benefits. These items indicate that a metaphorical language has been used in Daily Express. The term 'reerh ki haddi ki hasiyet' (like a backbone) is a metaphorical expression that is far from the factual measurement. This is a sign of exaggeration that makes it highly subjective and sentimental. The term 'sab se bra tarraqyati mansooba' (the biggest development project) used in Daily Jang is less sentimental as compared to Daily Express.

Example 3: Roshn mustaqbil ki naved vs. Barish ka pehla qatra (good news of bright future vs. the first rain drop)

In the above example, CPEC has been presented as 'roshn mustaqbil ki naved' (good news of bright future) in Daily Jang and 'barish ka pehla qatra' (the first rain drop) in Daily Express. Again, there is a metaphorical language used in Daily Express. The metaphors are used in newspapers to make the texts more interesting and rich, and to inspire certain feelings in readers" (Ghannam,

2011).

CPEC is figuratively described as the first rain drop, signalling the meaning of its benefits. In comparison to the expression "excellent news of a bright future," this is less accurate. Depending on the various elements linked with the project, the phrase 'news' may or may not come true in the future. The tone is neutral here, with no huge claims, but using CPEC as the first raindrop sounds less factual and more idealistic. Raindrop has a pleasant connotation, and it is utilised to transmit happiness in general. In comparison to Daily Jang, the sentimental tone in Daily Express is higher.

Example 4: Khatirkhuwah behtri vs. doorars or taveel mudatti fawaid (satisfactory betterment vs. Far-reaching and Long-term benefits)

Daily Jang described CPEC benefits as "Khatirkhuwah (satisfactory improvement)" and Daily Express described them as "doorars or taveel muddatti fawaid (far-reaching and long-term benefits). According to the Marium dictionary, the term 'far-reaching' is used to indicate a broad effect. Both the terms 'far-reaching' and 'long-term advantages' used in the Daily Express are examples of hyperbolic language that is less truthful. In comparison, the term 'satisfactory betterment' employed in Daily Jang is moderate in its presentation of CPEC to the audience.

Example 5: Khushali ki zamanat vs. khushali, aman or tarraqi k tanawar darakht se (Guarantee of Prosperity vs. from the bodied tree of Prosperity, Peace, and Progress)

With varied representations, the above vocabulary choices are likewise important to the ideology of PRO-CPEC. The word 'zamanat' (Guarantee) is a legal term that denotes the content's legitimacy. It was used in the Daily Jang for the prosperity that the CPEC project will bring to Pakistan, and it is guaranteed in the writer's opinion. In the Daily Express, on the other hand, the writer uses symbolic language to depict the CPEC project as a "bodied tree" with branches symbolising prosperity, peace, and progress. This could imply that the CPEC project will bring prosperity, peace, and progress to Pakistan. The Daily Express, on the other hand, portrays it as more emotional.

All of the preceding examples demonstrate how CPEC has been portrayed in different ways in Daily Jang and Daily Express news pieces. Lexicalization's overall conclusion is as follows:

- a. All newspapers have retained the pro-CPEC philosophy.
- b. The tone of Daily Jang is less sentimental than the tone of Daily Express.
- c. The Daily Express makes use of metaphors.
- d. When compared to Daily Express, Daily Jang's language was deemed to be more authentic and neutral.
- e. In comparison to Daily Jang, the Daily Express uses more exaggerated language.

4.3 Lexical Items in English & Urdu Newspapers: A Comparative Analysis

According to their emotional colouring, there are three categories of words as Zhang (2011) divided: commendatory words conveyed with active evaluation, derogatory words conveyed with negative evaluation, and neutral words conveyed with no evaluation. These categories were earlier discussed by Pu (2005). These categories help out in analyzing the hidden ideology in the lexical items. The category of the word used by an editor is a sign of his perception related to the news. It is observed in the current study that lexical items used for the economical subject (CPEC) fall into the category of the commendatory words in both English and Urdu newspapers. "The structure of a lexicon is important," says Fairclough (1989) based on ideology" (p. 115). Van Dijk (1988) contends, in a similar vein, that every newspaper reflects "opinion-controlled word choices." The use of commendatory words for CPEC in both English and Urdu newspapers is a sign of editor's favourable approach towards economic phenomenon of CPEC. PRO-CPEC ideology stands over here through the choice of commendatory words. The words 'game changer', 'way to progress', 'a jewel in the crown', 'mega project' used in English newspapers and the words used in Urdu newspapers like Khushali ki zamanat, barish ka pehla qatra, roshan mustaqbil ki naveed, and mulki mayishat mei reerh ki haddi ki hasiyet are all the agreeable words for the CPEC.

So, we can say that economic phenomenon has been portrayed in the same way in both the English and Urdu newspaper with the same ideology of PRO-CPEC.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this study was to uncover the editor's ideology through lexical choices that focused on ideologically contested terms. According to the study's results, there are several discrepancies in lexical choices. That is due to linguistic and cultural differences, as well as the author's worldview being represented.

The overall conclusions are:

- The ideology of PRO-CPEC ideology has been maintained in both English and Urdu newspapers
- The lexical items employed in Daily Dawn are very subjective with less integrity
- A balanced tone is reflected in THE NEWS newspaper while explaining the benefits of CPEC
- No harsh word in the form of commendatory words observed in both English and Urdu newspapers dealing with the subject CPEC

5.1 Future Implications

Critical discourse analysis has a vast scope in the field of research. The current study may be extended through comparing the findings of CPEC representation in local newspapers with the findings of CPEC

representation in international newspapers. Media discourse dealing with the same subject CPEC may be analyzed through the analytical tools other than lexicalization.

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